

Planning the Structure of a Dental Caries Prevention Program Using Discrete Event Simulation

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ABSTRACT

Dental caries disease is the most common infectious disease in the world. It affects people of all ages, but usually develops very early in children and occurs in both milk and permanent teeth. Its development can be slowed down or this disease can be completely eliminated through the use of properly selected preventive interventions. In this study, the process of implementation of a dental caries prevention program (DCPP) among elementary school students is modelled by discrete simulation method. Statistical parameters are derived from a nationwide study monitoring the oral health status of the Polish population and from research conducted in one primary school. Medical literature on the effectiveness of single preventive services was also analysed. The objective is to develop a simulation model that would make it possible to test the effectiveness of various structures of DCPP aimed at elementary school students during their education. Simulation experiments will also enable to forecast the anticipated workload of medical personnel required for a given program structure. Without prevention, about 78.2% of students graduate with four or more teeth with dental caries. Implementation of DCPP reduced this number to only 4.14%.

Key words: simulation modelling, discrete event simulation, decision-support, dental caries prevention

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization, disease prevention is defined as '*specific, population-based, and individual-based interventions for primary and secondary (early detection) prevention, aiming to minimise the burden of diseases and associated risk factors*' (WHO 2023). Such interventions are often delivered through preventive programmes addressing significant health issues. Notably, programme effectiveness can vary among populations owing to diverse needs, target group characteristics, resource availability, and expected health outcomes. Prevention programs are aimed at various diseases, among them are programs for the prevention of dental caries, targeted mainly at children and adolescents. Dental caries is a multifactorial bacterial disease that causes tooth tissue demineralisation (Featherstone 2000). This non-communicable ailment lacks a single cause and impacts health and quality of life (Mathur and Dhillon 2018). Dental caries is a major global non-communicable concern, affecting all ages and dentition types (WHO 2022). It is estimated that nearly 3.5 billion people worldwide suffer from dental caries.

Dental caries can be preventable through well-conceived prevention strategies. National measures, such as taxing sugar-sweetened beverages, also play a role in reducing the development of the disease (Stacey et al. 2017). Starting prevention early in childhood is pivotal. Interventions involve teeth fluoridation, sealing of the first molars, oral health and hygiene education (Ahovuo-Saloranta et al. 2013, Ahovuo-Saloranta et al. 2017, Lee 2013, Rong et al. 2003, Torices et al. 2021), delivered either individually or in group settings like schools. Implementing these interventions as part of well-planned and properly executed

prevention programs can bring significant benefits not only economically, but also in terms of public health. Proper caries prevention, implemented as early as possible, has a beneficial impact on children's future lives, oral health, and overall health (Stodolak and Fuglewicz 2014). Additionally, prevention is always cheaper than treatment (Wiśniewska-Sliwińska and Marcinkowski 2010). However, the question arises: how should such programs be planned to ensure long-term public health and savings resulting from the avoidance of treatments for the consequences of dental caries that have been prevented?

Effective planning of prevention programs requires balancing public health needs with resource constraints. Key considerations include defining objectives, allocating resources, identifying target populations, and assessing outcomes. Simulation models can aid in understanding tooth decay progression under different prevention strategies. In this context, program structure refers to the type, number, and frequency of preventive services provided. Simulation modelling can also help evaluate the effectiveness of various intervention sets.

This study presents a simulation model for designing the structure of a dental caries prevention program DCP and to determine the necessary staffing levels to achieve the desired health outcomes in primary school students. For this purpose, we employ discrete event simulation (DES), a widely used healthcare management approach (Katsaliaki and Mustafee 2011) that enables dynamic tracking of changes over time (Law and Kelton 1991). Given its ability to incorporate randomness, system dynamics, and service-outcome relationships, DES is well-suited for modelling dental caries prevention strategies.

In planning preventive programs, a significant aspect is the search for the relationship between the implementation of programs at a certain level of effectiveness and the necessary allocation of human resources for their implementation. It is important to understand how the magnitude of medical personnel resources and the choice of preventive services affect the feasibility of the planned program. The main challenge is to adjust the structure of a DCP so that, given a certain availability of human resources, to select services that effectively reduce the incidence of tooth decay among primary school students.

The objective of the study is to develop a simulation model that allows for the observation of students during their primary education and the changes occurring in their oral health as a result of the structure of the implemented DCP. The outcomes of the simulation model can support regional decision-makers and potentially enhance the design of such programs. The study not only contributes to the field of applying simulation modelling but also, through the development of a novel DES model, can contribute to better planning in the healthcare sector. It is built upon the research previously detailed in Hajłasz and Mielczarek (2022a, 2022b).

2. LITERATURE BACKGROUND

2.1. DES for Decision-Support in Various Prevention Programmes

The DES method is widely used to support the planning of prevention programs for various diseases, including those for financing, intervention selection, implementation strategies, and effectiveness evaluations. It helps assess the cost-effectiveness of cardiovascular disease prevention strategies by ranking patients by risk and inviting high-risk individuals to participate (Crossan et al., 2017). This approach evaluates costs and quality-adjusted life years, optimizing the choice of preventive strategies. Another study using DES evaluated the budgetary impact of hypothetical diabetes prevention programs, comparing the cost-effectiveness of different interventions (Kaasalainen et al., 2020).

Simulation models are essential for selecting the most effective interventions in prevention programs. Rauner et al. (2005) applied DES to assess interventions preventing mother-to-child HIV transmission in low-income countries. DES models the transmission dynamics and evaluates measures like antiretroviral therapy and breastfeeding practices, determining optimal

strategies. Given the challenges of underdeveloped infrastructure in many African regions, advanced methods like DES are crucial for effective decision-making (Rauner et al., 2005).

In addition, prevention programs for diseases like cervical cancer can reduce mortality and healthcare treatment costs (Tapia et al., 2021). A DES study showed that reducing screening result wait times from 60 to 2 days could expedite diagnosis and treatment, leading to improved outcomes. Efficiency and effectiveness evaluations are vital for effective program planning, as evidenced by Davies et al. (2002), who used DES to assess a *Helicobacter pylori* detection program. They evaluated the program's effectiveness through cost analysis and the years of life saved.

In summary, DES is widely used for planning and managing preventive programs for various diseases. It enables the tracking of disease progression and the impact of preventive interventions over time, while providing cost estimates and assessing health outcomes

2.2. Simulation Methods for Decision-Support in Dental Caries Prevention Programmes

Simulation methods are also used to support the planning of dental caries prevention programs (Table 1). The most common classification of simulation methods includes DES, agent-based simulation (ABS), system dynamics (SD), and Monte Carlo (MC) (Brailsford et al. 2009; Diallo et al. 2016; White and Ingalls 2020). Our review identified three main areas where these methods are applied to dental caries prevention programs: financing, intervention selection, and resource planning. Table 1 summarizes the methods and key areas identified in the literature. We conducted a search using terms like "management," "planning," "healthcare," "prevention," and "dental caries," identifying 2,019 papers. After reviewing abstracts, 36 were read in full, and 16 were included in this review.

Table 1: The application of simulation methods in identified areas of managing dental caries prevention programs.

Method \ Area	Financing	Interventions selection	Resource planning
DES			Scherrer et al. (2007)
ABS		Heaton et al. (2020)	
SD	Splieth and Fleßa (2008)	Edelstein et al. (2015) Hirsch et al. (2012) Urwannachotima et al. (2019) Urwannachotima et al. (2020)	Umeda et al. (2020)
MC	Boachie et al. (2023) Espinoza-Espinoza et al. (2019) Palacio et al. (2019) Khouja and Smith (2018) OConnell (2005) Norrie and Pharand (2020) Scherrer and Naavaal (2019) Schwendicke and Bombeck (2023)		

The area of programme financing addresses cost analysis and the economic impact of different DCPPs or the comparison of cost-effectiveness among strategies. This area stands out not only as the most extensive in terms of the number of scientific papers but also as the field with the highest growth in publications over time, particularly in the context of supporting the planning of DCPPs. The MC method dominates this field, often combined with decision trees and Markov models to evaluate different prevention strategies (Boachie et al., 2023; Espinoza-Espinoza et al., 2019; Norrie and Pharand, 2020). Splieth and Fleßa (2008) used SD to evaluate a fluoride-based program's effectiveness in preventing caries.

The intervention selection area explores how preventive measures can reduce dental caries and the effects of different policies on caries development. Heaton et al. (2020) used ABS to simulate the effectiveness of various interventions, including untreated caries and fluoridation. Edelstein et al. (2015) used SD to compare nine preventive interventions and their impact on caries reduction and net savings in New York City. Hirsch et al. (2012) identified the most effective interventions for reducing early childhood caries, while Urwannachotima et al. (2019, 2020) simulated the effects of policies like taxes on sugar-sweetened beverages in Thailand.

In the resource planning area, simulation methods are applied to optimize the use of material, human, and financial resources. DES was used by Scherrer et al. (2007) to find the best combination of staff and sealing stations for school-based dental sealant programs in the U.S., concluding that relaxing personnel restrictions could save money and increase program access. Umeda et al. (2020) used SD to plan resources for controlling early childhood caries, estimating the costs and clinical hours needed for different interventions.

Theoretical reflections led to the formulation of some conclusions. Simulation methods, including DES, offer valuable support for managing dental caries prevention programs. They capture complex interactions between preventive measures, resource constraints, and other factors influencing program effectiveness. While DES has been extensively applied in managing programs for other diseases, its use in dental caries prevention remains underexplored.

A detailed analysis of the literature shows that only one study (Scherrer et al., 2007) specifically applied DES to dental caries prevention management. However, numerous studies have used DES for managing other preventive health programs. This highlights the potential for expanding the use of DES in dental caries prevention. Decision-making in designing preventive services that maximize the number of primary school students graduating with minimal exposure to dental caries can be supported by utilizing DES. Developing a simulation model to test the effectiveness of various service combinations for DCPs in primary schools is a crucial step toward closing this gap.

3. SIMULATION MODEL

3.1. The process of providing a preventive program to students during their education

Primary education in Poland consists of eight grades. As part of the DCP, specific preventive interventions are provided to pupils each year (Figure 1). The baseline prevention program examined in this study includes the following services: dental check-ups, molar sealing (sixth and seventh teeth), supervised group fluoridation, and group education on oral health and hygiene. These services are delivered by medical professionals, including dentists, dental hygienists, and nursing staff (school nurses). Dentists are qualified to perform all interventions within the dental caries prevention program, while nurses are responsible for supervising fluoridation and providing education.

Figure 1: The real-world mechanism for delivering the DCP to primary school students in Poland.

3.2. Input Data

To accurately map disease progression, detailed medical data are essential, including the number of deciduous and permanent teeth among students and global indicators such as the percentage of the population affected by tooth decay. We also examined the number of decayed, missing, and filled primary (dmft) and permanent (DMFT) teeth. Since only aggregate data were available—expressed as the mean and variance for each age group—we couldn't fit distributions to individual measurements. Instead, we used the triangular distribution, which best represented our data, capturing natural variability and constraints for more realistic model outcomes. The study data came from various sources listed in Table 2, while Table 3 summarizes epidemiological data, including tooth count and dental caries prevalence.

Table 2: Data sources.

Data category	Source
Epidemiological	Wrocław Medical University and available literature reviews (Olczak-Kowalczyk et al. 2021a)
	Dental Caries Prevention Programme for Primary School Students in Wrocław (BIP 2024)
Demographic	Central Statistical Office (GUS 2022)
Effectiveness of preventive interventions	Available literature reviews (Marinho et al. 2015; Stein et al. 2018; Wright et al. 2016)
Duration of preventive interventions	Survey conducted among dentists (Hajłasz 2023)
	Available literature reviews (Olczak-Kowalczyk et al. 2021b)
	Knowledge and expert recommendations

Table 3: Epidemiological data for independent age groups for the Lower Silesian Voivodeship in Poland in years 2016-2020. For deciduous teeth, permanent teeth, dmft and DMFT: average and standard deviation (sd).

Parameter	Age [years]			
	7	10	12	15
Number of examinees	301	100	355	100
Children with at least one molar sealed	6.64%	16%	20.30%	9%
dmft/DMFT >0	75.75%	94%	87.04%	89%
Deciduous teeth	14.83 ± 2.85 (sd)	3.88 ± 3.77 (sd)	-	-
Permanent teeth	8.89 ± 2.87 (sd)	19.65 ± 4.03 (sd)	25.59 ± 2.94 (sd)	27.83 ± 0.79 (sd)
dmft	5.42 ± 3.25 (sd)	1.62 ± 1.88 (sd)	-	-
DMFT	0.61 ± 1.12 (sd)	1.88 ± 1.63 (sd)	3.6 ± 2.74 (sd)	5.42 ± 3.69 (sd)

Source: Olczak-Kowalczyk et al. (2021a).

3.3. Model assumptions – the overall structure of the DCP

3.3.1. Services provided

Dental caries can be prevented through properly targeted and well-executed preventive care. Effective measures include tooth fluoridation, sealing of first molars, screening tests, and education (Ahovuo-Saloranta et al., 2013; Ahovuo-Saloranta, 2017; Lee, 2013; Rong et al., 2023; Sosa Torices et al., 2021; Sicca et al., 2016). The simulation model presented in this paper incorporates these four interventions, following recommendations from the relevant literature.

3.3.2. Staff responsible for a prevention programme

Dental examinations and molar sealing are carried out by dentists, whereas group-supervised fluoridation and education sessions are overseen by nurses or dental hygienists. Dental check-ups are scheduled twice a year, followed by molar sealing if deemed necessary.

3.3.3. A time durations of interventions

The durations of the interventions were gathered from various sources, as shown in Table 4. The time required for sealing can vary depending on factors such as the number of teeth needing treatment and the student's level of cooperation, as determined from survey data. Fluoridation is administered six times a year, at six-week intervals (Ostręga et al., 2020), and is conducted for the entire class at once. The duration of fluoridation was based on direct observations. Oral health education is provided biannually, with each session lasting approximately 45 minutes. For students in seventh and eighth grades, there is one extended session lasting 90 minutes annually, followed by regular 45-minute sessions (Olczak-Kowalczyk et al., 2021b). The durations of individual activities were modelled using triangular and uniform distributions, as these best represented the available aggregated data.

Table 4: Incorporated preventive interventions in the model: duration, source, and implementation approach.

Intervention	Specialist	Duration [minutes]	Source	Distribution implemented in the model
Dental check-up	dentist	5–15 (per one student)	The survey	Triangular 5–15 (the most likely value: 15)
First molar sealing	dentist	5–15 (per one tooth)	The survey	Triangular 5–15 (the most likely value: 10)
Group-supervised fluoridation	nurse	10–20 (per class)	Expert knowledge	Uniform 10–20
Oral health education	nurse	40-50 (per class) or 85-95 (per class)	Olczak-Kowalczyk (2021b)	Uniform 40–50 (or 85–95 for one session in the seventh and eighth grades)

3.3.4. Dental caries progression

The simulation model replicates the progression of dental caries in schoolchildren. It observes how oral health status changes among students both when they do not receive dental care services and when various preventive program scenarios are implemented. Using source data (see Table 3) for students at specific ages (7, 10, 12, and 15), we generate values for oral health indicators based on triangular distributions corresponding to each student's age. The average values from empirical data are taken as the most likely values, with the minimum value calculated by subtracting the standard deviation from the mean, and the maximum by adding the standard deviation. We ensure that indicator values remain within logical limits, i.e., they cannot be less than zero or exceed the number of teeth present in the mouth. The progression of dental caries is measured as the difference between the future and current values generated by the triangular distributions. To calculate the average annual increase, this difference is divided by the number of years between the data age points.

The medical assumptions incorporated into the simulation model are based on reputable academic sources. Health education is recognized as an effective service for significantly preventing the development of dental caries (Stein et al., 2018). Fluoridation reduces the risk of cavities by 20% for primary teeth surfaces and 28% for permanent teeth (Marinho et al., 2015). In contrast, dental sealants reduce the risk of cavities in permanent teeth by 79% (Wright et al., 2016). Drawing on these values and consulting with a dental specialist, we incorporate the efficacy of caries prevention interventions into the simulation scenarios (odds ratio [OR], 0.15; 95% confidence interval [CI], 0.08–0.27).

3.3.5. Student characteristics

After comparing the DMFT index values for students in Lower Silesia (Olczak-Kowalczyk, 2021a), we excluded gender-based divisions. In the model, students are assigned values for six key attributes: the number of primary and permanent teeth, dmft and DMFT index values, as well as year cohort and class identifiers. The total number of teeth and the number of teeth

affected by caries are updated at the end of each year. These values are modelled using triangular distributions, with generated values adjusted to whole numbers, always greater than zero. The number of decayed teeth cannot exceed the total number of deciduous or permanent teeth, and the number of permanent teeth cannot exceed 28.

3.3.6. Beginning of pupils' primary education

Every year, 100 new students begin their education in five parallel classes. Students are generated individually and then grouped into classes, navigating the system as a wholeclass. The education lasts eight years, reflecting the duration of primary school in Poland. We envisioned a static class structure, where students participate in all preventive interventions. Although most Polish students typically start school around the age of seven, variations in starting age, grade repetition, or birth dates were deemed minor in the context of this study. Therefore, students begin their education at age seven, age by one year annually, and complete their primary education at age fourteen.

3.3.7. A calendar

We analysed school calendars from 2011 to 2021. While there were annual fluctuations, a consistent pattern was evident. In our model, we adopted the calendar for the 2021/2022 academic year as representative. It was assumed that students would participate in preventive services on weekdays.

3.3.8. Output Measures

The primary objective of this study is to develop a simulation model that allows for testing the effectiveness of various structures of DCPs. Key output indicators of the simulation include the dmft and DMFT indices, as well as the hours of medical staff required to deliver a preventive programme for a specific cohort throughout primary education. Whilst the dmft and DMFT indices remain standard medical benchmarks, planners might consider a boarded perspective when designing prevention programmes. This could involve stratifying the disease into different stages. For our simulation, we introduce the Dental Caries State (DCS). Based on the combined values of dmft and DMFT, the DCS can be categorised as ‘good’, ‘moderate’, or ‘bad’ (Table 5). Once deciduous teeth are no longer considered, the contribution of dmft to determining the DCS is regarded as negligible.

Table 5: Classification and short description of Dental Caries State based on the sum of dmft and DMFT indicators.

DCS	dmft + DMFT	Description
Good	0	The most desirable state, indicating that the student has no teeth affected by caries.
Moderate	from 1 to 3	The acceptable state, signifying that students have between one and three teeth affected by caries.
Bad	4 and more	The unacceptable state, indicating that students have four or more teeth with caries.

3.3.9. Simulation Parameters

The prevention programme targets all pupils in the school at every level of education, with its outcomes observed annually. However, the completion of the eighth grade is particularly important to verify the effectiveness of the programme. For this reason, we considered it essential to treat the process under investigation as a steady-state system. To avoid potential underestimation of results, an 8-year warm-up – corresponding to a full primary education cycle – was defined. The replication duration depends on the number of evaluated graduating cohorts. For a single cohort, one replication covers 16 years, including of the warm-up phase. With two, three, or four cohorts, the durations extend to 17, 18, and 19 years, respectively.

We proposed a 20-year period for one replication to observe the full education cycle for students starting school over five consecutive years. This period also includes the 8-year warm-up period. A total of 10 replications were conducted.

4. SIMULATION STUDY

4.1. Computer Model

Based on the assumptions outlined in the previous section, a computer model was developed. Using the DES method, the progression of dental caries in students during their primary school education was modelled. The preliminary version of the model was presented in Hajłasz and Mielczarek (2022c). The simulation model was built using a visual interactive simulation software, Arena by Rockwell Software version 16.1, and documented according to the Strengthening the Reporting of Empirical Simulation Studies (STRESS) checklist (Monks et al. 2019). The full STRESS documentation is provided in the appendix (Appendix 1). The computer model, along with the input data, has been made available in an open data repository (Hajłasz 2024a). Figure 2 illustrates a simplified logic diagram of the constructed simulation model.

Figure 2: A simplified diagram of the logical model describing the provision of the Dental Caries Prevention Programme to students in primary school during their education process.

Time control in simulation

The model includes a special component responsible for tracking the current day of the calendar year. Upon starting the simulation, a single object representing the day is generated. As it progresses through the blocks, the "day" variable increases by 1 until it reaches 365, at which point it resets to 0, and a new year begins. Additionally, a variable that sums the number of days since the start of the simulation increments. When this variable reaches 7300, the object exits the system, and the simulation ends. Tracking the current day in the simulation serves several purposes. First, it relates to the school year calendar, determining whether a day is a school day or a holiday based on the "day" variable. Second, it controls whether it is a day for fluoridation. Third, it verifies the interval between dental check-ups.

Pupils

Students, represented as discrete objects, enter the school in five streams, with each stream representing a class they attend throughout their primary education. In total, one hundred new objects are generated each year. Students move through the model as a whole class, but when necessary, they are considered as individuals and then regrouped into classes.

Students are assigned attributes that describe their characteristics and oral health status (the list of attributes can be found in Appendix 1). After attribute assignment, students are grouped into their respective classes and proceed as five cumulative objects representing five parallel classes per year. Each student is assigned initial values for key indicators relevant to dental caries assessment. The included values for primary and permanent teeth indicators, dmft, DMFT, and the sealed teeth indicator, which is based on the probability of having at least one sealed first molar. The values for these parameters are generated from triangular distributions based on real data.

Provision of services

At the beginning of each school year, some time must pass before students begin receiving preventive services. After the start of each school year, for each class individually, a random number of days is generated ranging from ten to thirty days, with the most common value being fifteen days.

Directing students to preventive services requires several conditions to be met: it must be a school day, a weekday, and there must be planned services yet to be provided that school year. Once these conditions are met, further checks are performed based on specific preventive services. Fluoridation and group education are provided to the entire class, while dental check-ups and sealants are given individually.

Fluoridation follows a predefined schedule. The day for fluoridation is checked first, and students undergo fluoridation if the current day matches the scheduled day (± 1 day). After some fluoridations, group education may follow, with a 50% chance after each of the six annual fluoridations, ensuring two group sessions per year. If no group education session has occurred, the last two fluoridations will guarantee a session. If it's not a fluoridation day, the conditions for dental check-ups are checked. Students receive two check-ups annually. For the first check-up, the dentist must be available, and no prior check-up should have occurred that year. For the second check-up, the dentist must be available, and at least 3-6 months should have passed since the last check-up. The dentist also checks for new molars (sixth and/or seventh) and seals them if they are not already sealed.

After any service, the model verifies if all planned services for the year have been completed. If so, students update their health indicators and wait for the school year to end, with each condition check taking one day.

Dentists provide check-ups and sealants, while school nurses or dental hygienists handle fluoridation and group education. Both work on weekdays, with dentists working six hours and nurses eight hours per day. If a service extends beyond working hours, it continues the next following workday.

Updating pupil health indicators

The indicator for the number of sealed teeth is updated after a student's dental visit. Other oral health indicators (number of primary teeth, permanent teeth, dmft, and DMFT) are updated at the end of each school year, after all preventive services have been completed, individually for each student, eight times throughout their education. General settings, such as the number of provided services and class indicators, are also updated annually.

Oral health indicators are updated based on real data. The effectiveness of preventive services measured by the reduction in potential dental caries. At the end of each school year, a

parameter for the effectiveness of fluoridation and group education is generated for each student. This parameter indicates the reduction in the number of new carious teeth due to preventive care. For instance, if the effectiveness is 0.25, it means a 25% reduction in new carious teeth.

Students with existing carious teeth update their indicators first. For others, the model checks for new carious teeth each year, applying the generated effectiveness to reduce the growth of new carious teeth.

Next, the model checks whether students have sealed permanent teeth and whether new carious teeth appear despite the preventive measures. The effectiveness of sealants is measured by the probability that sealed teeth remain caries-free, generated annually. If sealants are effective, no new carious teeth will appear in sealed teeth. If caries growth exceeds the number of sealed teeth, the growth is reduced by the number of sealed teeth. For example, if a student has four sealed teeth but expects two new carious teeth, those two teeth will remain healthy due to the sealants. In the next evaluation, these two teeth will not be considered at risk for caries.

Variance reduction

One of the characteristics of the DES method is randomness, meaning that the output data from the model result from the random input data implemented (Law and Kelton 1991). Therefore, appropriate variance reduction techniques should be applied to ensure the correct interpretation of the results. For example, the Common Random Numbers (CRN) method ensures similar experimental conditions and increases confidence that any observed differences result from the assumptions made, rather than random factors. The CRN method was used in our model. In each experiment, the same initial values were used for four main indicators: the number of primary teeth, the number of permanent teeth, dmft, and DMFT. Four sequences of random numbers were then utilized to generate the values of these indicators, with one sequence corresponding to each indicator. Any changes in the values of the indicators were derived from these sequences.

Sensitivity analysis

In studies like ours, which involve multiple elements with a random nature, conducting sensitivity analysis (SA) is an essential step. SA is a technique used to assess whether, and to what extent, changes in specific variables influence a model's outcome (Walker and Fox-Rushby 2001). Various techniques can be employed for this purpose, including one-way and multi-way SA. One-way SA examines the impact of changes in a single variable on the model's outcome while keeping all other variables constant. In contrast, multi-way analysis investigates how simultaneous changes in multiple variables affect the model's results. In our study, we conducted a one-way SA, which identified caries progression rates as the most sensitive factor in our model (the SA results can be found in Appendix 2).

4.2. Verification and Validation

The model underwent comprehensive verification and validation following Naylor's (1975) three-step evaluation concept. The consulted dentists approved the model, recognizing its utility in supporting dental caries prevention planning. To ensure its accuracy, we conducted a thorough series of tests, a selection of which is outlined in Table 6.

Table 6: Selected verification tests with descriptions and their pass/fail status.

Test Name	Test Description	Status
Inflow/outflow test	Verification to ensure that student inflow and outflow align with our assumptions: students expected to leave the model during the simulation do so, while those expected to remain stay in the model. Specifically, all students who have spent 8 years at the school should exit, while those in grades 1-8 should remain.	Passed
Service compliance test	Verification if all planned services, such as dental check-ups, fluoridations, educational sessions, and sealant applications, were carried out. The services are scheduled in accordance with the preventive care program established for each school year, tailored to students of the respective age group.	Passed
Sealant eligibility test	Verification of whether recommended students receive sealants and have the correct number of teeth sealed. A student who should have their teeth sealed is one who has molars (sixes and/or sevens, depending on the experiments) and during the dental check-up, the dentist confirms that they are not sealed.	Passed

During model validation, we compare the average simulated results with empirical data based on specific descriptive indicators: primary teeth, permanent teeth, dmft, and DMFT in the Lower Silesia region. We ensure that the model's mean fell within the range of the actual mean and deviation. The simulation results were consistent with real-world data. Figure 3 illustrates an example for each index across different student age groups.

Figure 3: Validating mean numbers of deciduous and permanent teeth, along with dmft and DMFT indexes, an example for each index across different student age groups.

Additionally, we verify that the model's percentage of students affected by tooth decay aligns with real-world data (Figure 4). The model accurately reflects the actual percentage of students with dental caries.

Figure 4: Comparison of dental caries occurrence percentages among students aged 7, 10, 12, and 15: actual data versus the mean of 10 replications.

4.3. Plan of Experiments

Each simulation experiment consists of 10 replications. The number of replications was determined using the confidence interval method. Each replication lasts 7300 days (20 years),

which includes 2920 days (8 years) of the warm-up period. After the warm-up period, we collect statistics for the full cycle of education for five cohorts of students starting their education in subsequent years.

The main goal of the simulation experiments is to observe the progression of dental caries in primary school students over time and under the influence of prevention programmes with varied hypothetical structures and different number of services provided. The entire simulation experiment is run in two stages. In phase one, five scenarios are run (Table 7). In phase two, the selected scenarios of phase one are further modified and run again.

In the baseline scenario, we assume no interventions, allowing dental caries to progress based on actual data (see Table 7; Scenario 0). In subsequent experiments, the selection of interventions provided by a nurse and/or doctor is differentiated (Table 7). In the Scenario 1, we explore the development of dental caries among students under a full set of interventions included in the preventive program. In the Scenario 2, the full set of services was reduced by excluding the sealing of the second molars. Since this is a time-consuming task requiring the engagement of a doctor for each student individually, it is interesting to examine whether sealing only the first molars, instead of both first and second molars, will significantly affect the worsening of health outcomes in students and the doctor's working time if students are provided with the remaining services. In the Scenario 3, we assumed that students are provided only with group services conducted by a nurse, while in Scenarios 4 and 5, we assumed that the preventive program includes two or three services provided exclusively by a dentist.

In addition to five main scenarios, we also explored what would happen if students had fewer group oral health education talks. Therefore, this adjustment was applied in the second stage of simulation experiments to Scenarios 1, 2, and 3, where these talks were included. By default, students always have two talks per year and these occur after fluoridations, of which there are always six. After fluoridations 1 to 4 in a given year, there was a 50% chance that a given group of students would have a talk at that time. If during the 5th talk they still had not had any in that year, the probability of having an educational session after the 5th and 6th talk was equal to one. In the adjustment of the experiments, we assumed that after each fluoridation there was only a 30% chance that the students would have a talk. This resulted in some years where students had two talks, sometimes one, and sometimes none at all. The absence of talks in a given year could additionally reduce the baseline effectiveness of interventions provided by a nurse.

Table 7: Interventions included in simulation scenarios. An asterisk next to the scenario number indicates that additional experiments were conducted for this scenario, which involved reducing the number of educational talks.

Scenario	group-supervised fluoridation	oral health education	dental check-ups	sealing of the sixth teeth	sealing of seventh teeth
0					
1*	V	V	V	V	V
2*	V	V	V	V	
3*	V	V			
4			V	V	V
5			V	V	

In the experiments, we assume that the effectiveness of fluoridation and educational talks is generated annually from distributions with consistent parameters (Table 8). The distributions are based on the effectiveness reported in the literature. Effectiveness refers to the reduction in potential number of teeth with dental caries that could occur if these interventions are not implemented. Even if teeth are sealed, there may still be cases where decay develops despite the sealing. However, this occurs in a reduced group of students, ranging from 10% to 44% of the cohort. Based on the available data, we believe that the triangular distribution best represents these data.

Table 8: Parameters of the random distributions used to generate the effectiveness of group-supervised fluoridation and educational talks for deciduous and permanent teeth at the end of each school year, individually for each student.

Teeth	Triangular distribution parameters
Deciduous	0.2–0.3 (the most likely value: 0.25)
Permanent	0.28–0.38 (the most likely value: 0.35)

4.4. Results and Discussion

4.4.1. Main scenarios

In each experiment, we consider various structures of DCPPs for primary school students. In Table 9, we presented the average percentage of students finishing school with good, moderate, and bad DCS. In the following analysis of the results, we will focus on the examination of bad DCS. Depending on the design of the prevention program, different average numbers of students with bad DCS during primary education were achieved. (Figure 5).

Table 9: Experimental results (first stage) - percentage of students with DCS good, moderate and bad at the end of primary school education. Mean of 10 replications for a group of 500 students.

Scenario	DCS good	DCS moderate	DCS bad
0	13.02%	8.78%	78.2%
1	26.40%	69.46%	4.14%
2	23.92%	62.52%	13.56%
3	16.84%	47.20%	35.96%
4	20.38%	48.04%	31.58%
5	15.70%	21.76%	62.54%

Figure 5: Results from all conducted simulation scenarios: the average number of students with bad DCS [%] throughout the education period for a group of 500 students: Scenario 0 - 78.2%, Scenario 1 - 4.14%, Scenario 2 - 13.56%, Scenario 3 - 35.96%, Scenario 4 - 31.58%, Scenario 5 - 62.54%.

Figure 5 demonstrates that, compared to the absence of any preventive programme (scenario 0), a preventive program of any structure resulted in a decrease in the average number of students finishing school with bad DCS. To determine whether including various services in dental caries prevention programs significantly affects the average health outcomes of students finishing primary education, a dependent t-test was applied to compare the mean values of bad

DCS indicators across 10 simulation replications. The tests were performed at a significance level of 0.05.

In each comparison between scenario 0 and scenarios 1 through 5, the mean values for the “bad DCS” indicator were notably lower in the groups with preventive programmes. The dependent t-tests indicated statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) for each scenario pair, with high t-statistic values reflecting the strong impact of preventive programs in reducing the “bad DCS” indicator among primary school students. The most comprehensive programmes (scenarios 1 and 2) resulted in 4.14% and 13.56% of students, respectively, finishing school with bad DCS. Implementing a program designed according to scenarios 3 and 4 would allow a similar percentage of students, specifically 35.96% and 31.58% respectively in scenarios 3 and 4, to finish school with bad DCS. The worst results among all tested DCP structures would result from the implementation of the program from scenario 5, where 62.54% of students would finish school with bad DCS.

Figure 5 shows that the curves align with the same trends. In scenario 0, there is a significant decline up to the third year of education, followed by a rise of varying intensity up to the eighth year. A similar behavior occurs with the curves for scenarios 1 to 5, except that the curves decline until the fourth or fifth year of education and then rise with varying intensity depending on the experiment. This trend is likely related to the loss of deciduous teeth, as the loss of a decayed deciduous tooth reduces the bad DCS for a given student. According to the literature, by the age of 12, students usually no longer have deciduous teeth, so depending on many random factors, including the services provided within preventive programs, they may develop decayed teeth sooner, later, or not at all.

Each of the structures tested in the scenarios required the involvement of medical personnel responsible for carrying out the planned services. Table 10 shows the annual and average workload of a dentist and a nurse required to provide services for a group of 500 students in each program. Due to the repetitiveness of the services, the dentist's working time is the same in scenarios 1 and 4, as well as 2 and 5. Similarly, in all scenarios where the nurse's services are utilized (i.e., scenarios: 1 – 3), the required working time remains the same to ensure the same set of services.

Table 10: Medical staff time required to provide a group of 500 students with DCP as assumed in all scenarios, specifying the working time of doctors and nurses in each scenario: average \pm 95% confidence interval.

Medical staff	Scenario	Year of education							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Dentist	1 and 4	826.82 (± 5.83)	206.07 (± 1.75)	194.34 (± 0.66)	195.01 (± 0.93)	194.88 (± 0.64)	194.27 (± 0.62)	194.42 (± 0.47)	194.67 (± 0.56)
	2 and 5	505.46 (± 3.93)	194.98 (± 0.64)	195.54 (± 1.52)	194.31 (± 0.69)	194.64 (± 1.42)	194.36 (± 0.77)	194.71 (± 1.05)	194.27 (± 0.73)
Nurse	1, 2 and 3	74.93 (± 0.3)	75.33 (± 0.32)	74.64 (± 0.36)	75.16 (± 0.33)	75.16 (± 0.31)	74.61 (± 0.37)	94 (± 0.7)	93.51 (± 0.48)

The workload of the dentist is heaviest during the first years of students' education because, during this time, in addition to dental checkups, the dentist also seals the sixth molars (in scenarios 2 and 5) and both the sixth and seventh molars (in scenarios 1 and 4). Afterwards, the time spent on checkups each year amounts to about 194 hours annually. The workload of the nurse is similar in the first years of students' education, contributing about 74 hours per year. However, in the 7th and 8th years of education, the working time is longer because older children are provided with longer educational talks.

Certainly, the most comprehensive program would achieve the best health outcomes, as confirmed by reality and demonstrated by our model. Implementing the most comprehensive program would require an average annual workload of 275.06 hours for doctors and 79.67 hours for nurses. However, there may be situations where, due to limited human and financial

resources, it is not feasible to implement such a comprehensive program for students in school. In such cases, one might consider services provided by just one type of specialist. Figure 6 showed that Scenario 3, where only a nurse provided services, could achieve health outcomes very close to those in Scenario 4, where services were provided by a doctor. The differences between the mean results obtained in scenarios 3 and 4 are statistically significant, as confirmed by the dependent t-test with a p-value of 0.0004 for the two-tailed test. In these scenarios, the time a nurse would need to dedicate to students was significantly less than that required by a doctor. In addition, the nurse's time is less expensive than the doctor's. Therefore, with limited resources, it might be advisable to consider implementing a program structured like Scenario 3.

4.4.2. Scenario Adjustments

In this chapter, we present the results of the second phase of experiments for those scenario variants where we assumed a reduced involvement of nurses (scenarios 1, 2, and 3). Compared to the previously described results for the first phase scenarios, we varied the number of educational talks. Figure 6 shows that a reduced number of educational talks negatively impacted the average number of students finishing school with bad DCS. The largest difference is noticeable when students receive only nursing services, as in scenario 3, while in scenario 1, with the most comprehensive structure, the difference is the smallest.

Figure 6: Results from three adjusted simulation scenarios (on average 34.2 educational talks per year) in comparison to scenarios from the first stage of experiments (50 educational talks per year): the average number of students [%] with bad DCS at the end of the education period for a group of 500 students.

Under the basic assumptions, students receive two educational talks annually. Assuming they receive fewer than the baseline, there could be 0, 1, or 2 talks per class each year. The reduction in the number of educational talks conducted annually by the nurse for a group of students led to 35 talks instead of 50 (Table 11). This decrease correlates with a reduced demand for the nurse's work hours, dropping from an average of 79.67 hours per year for 50 talks to 69.03 hours for the reduced number. However, despite this significant reduction in talks, the decrease in work hours is relatively minor, while the negative impact on health outcomes is substantial. This raises the question of whether cutting back on talks is truly beneficial, as it saves only a few work hours for the nurse but significantly worsens students' health outcomes.

Table 11: The average annual number of group educational talks on oral health and hygiene conducted by the nurse for a group of 500 students throughout their primary school education, along with the corresponding annual work hours required to deliver a reduced number of talks (consistent across the three analysed scenarios).

Year of education	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Number of educational talks	35 (±3.37)	36.5 (±2.87)	36.1 (±1.45)	34.2 (±2.71)	37.8 (±3.05)	36.4 (±2.29)	37.1 (±2.73)	37.5 (±2.72)
Average working time of a nursing staff	64 (±2.58)	64,75 (±2.42)	64.43 (±1.29)	63.23 (±2)	65.85 (±2.53)	65.23 (±1.68)	82.13 (±2.88)	82.64 (±3.18)

Depending on the structure of the implemented DCP, different health outcomes are possible. A benchmark for determining the effectiveness of DCP can be the assumption that students are provided with services of basic effectiveness, as in the scenario 1. Achieving the desired effects requires the commitment of different medical staff resources. Providing all the interventions under consideration allows for a multifaceted action aimed at preventing dental caries. At the same time, it requires a high level of involvement of specialists, compared to the smaller scope of the program. Depending on the available resources and individual goals defined for prevention programs dedicated to students in specific primary school, different interventions may be delivered. The simulation model can support the development of a program structure that potentially achieves the intended health outcomes.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We developed and presented the simulation model to test the effectiveness of various structures of DCPs targeting primary school students over the course of their eight-year education. The model allowed us to observe both the health outcomes of students and the workload of medical and nursing staff required to implement programmes of different structures. The results indicated that more comprehensive programmes, which include services provided by both doctors and nurses, were most effective in reducing the average number of students finishing primary school with an alarmingly high number of decayed teeth (four or more decayed teeth). While, these insight might seem intuitive, the simulation model provides a deeper understanding of the relationship between the human resources required and the expected outcomes of the programme.

When resources, such as human capital, are limited, the question arises: how to provide a dental caries prevention program to a group of students that would potentially yield the best outcomes with limited resources? The model we developed enables us to explore the impact of different sets of services provided to students, considering the individual effects on each student.

This study demonstrates how simulation can serve as a decision-support tool for planning various aspects of DCPs, including human resource allocation and the organization of preventive services. By applying Discrete Event Simulation (DES), we support the planning of specialized services for primary school students over the eight-year educational cycle in Poland. The model provides a way to evaluate different program structures, taking into account human resource constraints, and assessing how specific structures might reduce the incidence of dental caries among children as they complete primary school.

Our research addresses a critical gap in the field and highlights an important area for further exploration: the integration of cost analysis into preventive program planning. Preventive services vary in their delivery methods, with some services provided individually and others in group settings. The simulation framework we propose offers a valuable way to evaluate which approach—individual or group services—is more cost-effective in terms of expenses, resource utilization, and health outcomes.

The proposed model is flexible and can be expanded or adapted to meet the specific needs of different regions and research objectives. Sensitivity Analysis (SA) revealed a significant dependence of the observed outcomes on the parameters governing the progression of tooth decay in students. Consequently, conclusions derived from the model should not be generalized without caution. It is essential to carefully select distribution parameters based on real-world data that reflect the characteristics of the region under study, ensuring that the decision-making process remains accurate and reliable.

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DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

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APPENDIX

APPENDIX 1: STRESS Checklist, section along with detailed elements (Monks et al. 2019).

Objectives	
Purpose of the model	The model outputs are described in section 4.1.
Model outputs	The model outputs are described in section 3.3.8.
Experimentation aims	The model outputs are described in section 4.3.
Logic	
Base model overview diagram	A simplified base diagram of the model is presented in section 3.1, Figure 1.
Base model logic	A simplified base diagram of the model is presented in section 3.1, Figure 2.
Scenario logic	The concept of the scenarios is described in section 4.3, Table 7.
Algorithms	The algorithms used in the model are described in section 4.1.
Components	<p>Entities – In the model, there are two types of entities: day and student. The day is an object generated once upon the initiation of the simulation. Its function is to control the passage of simulated time. Within the second type of entities, the student is specified. At the beginning of each school year, dynamic objects representing students are generated, who stay in the model for the duration of their primary school education. Each student is assigned their individual attributes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Class - Each student is assigned a symbol from one of the five classes in a given year. • Year of Education - Each student has an assigned current year of their education in primary school. • Deciduous Teeth - Each student has an assigned current number of deciduous teeth, which fall out over time. • Permanent Teeth - Each student has an assigned current number of permanent teeth, which changes as new permanent teeth emerge in the student's oral cavity. • Sealed Teeth¹ - The number of sealed teeth a student has. Students can have up to four or eight permanent molar teeth sealed. • dmft² Index - Information about the number of deciduous teeth with decay, missing, and fillings. The dmft index may increase with the appearance of new carious lesions and decrease as deciduous teeth fall out. • DMFT Index - Information about the number of permanent teeth with decay, missing, and fillings. The DMFT index may increase with the appearance of new carious lesions. <p>Activities – all students start their education in the first grade of primary school. They attend school for eight years, advancing to the next grade each year (from 1 to 8). Every year, students receive preventive services as planned within the dental caries prevention program. Some services are provided individually to students, while others are delivered in a group setting (involving the entire class).</p> <p>Resources – two types of resources can be identified: medical staff and nursing staff. Both medical and nursing staff work according to schedules (medical staff for 6 hours, nursing staff for 8 hours per day on weekdays) and provide preventive services to students.</p>

¹ Students have four teeth sealed when the preventive service includes sealing the sixth molars, and eight teeth are sealed when the service covers both the sixth and seventh molars.

² The dmft/DMFT indices indicate the number of teeth with decay, those that have been extracted, and those filled due to caries (dmft, written in lowercase, refers to deciduous teeth, while DMFT, written in uppercase, refers to permanent teeth).

	<p>Queues – the principle for selecting requests from queues is based on the First In, First Out (FIFO) method.</p> <p>Entry/Exit Points – every year, a specific number of students enter the model and begin their education. After eight years, students complete their education and exit the model.</p>
Data	
Data sources	The data sources are described in section 3.2.
Input parameters	The data sources are described in section 3.2.
Pre-processing	The input data presented averages and deviations from the mean. In the model, these data were implemented using triangular distributions, which proved to be the most adequately selected distributions for representing the number of deciduous teeth, permanent teeth, and dmft and DMFT indices. The minimum value of the distributions was calculated based on the actual average and deviation from this average. If the result was a negative value, the minimum parameter of the distribution was set to 0.01. Conversely, if the maximum value—calculated as the average plus deviation—for the number of deciduous teeth exceeded 28 ³ , then 28 was adopted as the maximum parameter of the triangular distribution.
Assumptions	Assumptions are described in section 3.3.
Experimentation	
Initialisation	A steady-state analysis was conducted, setting a warm-up period equal to eight years of education to ensure the entire school was filled with students.
Run length	The assumptions regarding the length of repetition are described in section 3.3.9.
Estimation approach.	For each scenario, 10 repetitions were conducted based on the confidence interval analysis method. Interval estimation was used, rather than point estimation.
Implementation	
Software or programming language	The computer model was programmed using a software tool based on the SIMAN language. The Arena version 16.1 environment by Rockwell Automation, which is a visual-interactive simulation (VIS) platform, was used.
Random sampling	Random numbers are generated from four streams of pseudo-random numbers using generators in Arena.
Model execution.	In the study, discrete event simulation (DES) was used to dynamically model the flow of students from the beginning to the end of their education in primary school.
System specification	<p>To run the model in the Arena program on a computer, the system must meet the requirements specified on the software manufacturer's website (Rockwell Automation Software, 2024). The model was executed on a computer with the following specifications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processor: 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-11850H • RAM: 32 GB • Operating System: Windows 11 <p>On this computer, conducting a single simulation experiment consisting of 10 replications in fast-forward mode took approximately 10 seconds.</p>
Code access	
Computer model sharing statement	The model has been published in an open data repository (Hajłasz 2024).

APPENDIX 2: The SA results

Since our research focuses on understanding how various structures of DCPD affect the percentage of students graduating with bad DCS, we explore this critical aspect. We present three variants to demonstrate how differences in progression rates affect students' dental health by the end of primary education

³ According to medical knowledge, students should not have more than 28 teeth by the time they finish school

In Variant I, using standard assumptions (section 3.3.4), we projected caries progression for each student. If a generated future DMFT value exceeded the current DMFT, we calculated the difference and used it to estimate caries progression. This scenario yielded an average of 391 students (confidence interval (CI): ± 7.34) with bad dental caries status (DCS), or 78.2% of the population, reflecting moderate progression.

In Variant II, we assumed caries progression would still follow a triangular distribution, using the same data and the range of the distribution as in Variant I. However, here, the minimum value was the most likely, reflecting a lower likelihood of progression in each distribution. This approach reduced the number of students with bad DCS to 268.2 (CI: ± 8.78), or 53.64%, suggesting better outcomes under slower progression assumptions.

In Variant III, we again used a triangular distribution but set the maximum as the most common value, indicating a higher likelihood of caries progression. Faster progression rate increased the projected number of students with bad DCS to 424.1 (CI: ± 7.57), or 84.82%.

In summary, the range from 53.64% in Variant II to 84.82% in Variant III highlights how the most common value of the distribution affects outcomes. This variation underscores the impact of different progression rates on dental health and the potential benefits of preventive interventions to mitigate faster caries progression.